

MAIN FUNCTIONS OF PHRASEMES AND PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS IN EMPATHETIC SPEECH

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Abstract: This research paper discusses the use and primary functions of phraseologisms and paremiological units within the structure of empathetic speech, which is one of the forms of ethical-aesthetic discourse. The arguments presented are supported with excerpts from literary texts.

Keywords: empathetic sema, phraseme, paremiological unit, speech, empathy, consolation, comfort, aesthetic speech, etc.

In today's globalized world, societal changes inevitably affect the field of science, particularly linguistics. As society and science evolve, new dimensions of various disciplines are continually discovered. Modern linguists pay special attention not only to the structure and functions of speech but also to its ethical-aesthetic genres. Speech units in the Uzbek language appear across various discourses. Accordingly, ethical-aesthetic types of speech in Uzbek can be classified as expressions of gratitude, irony, consolation, forgiveness, anger, affection, praise, empathy, protest, and reproach.

One of these genres, empathetic speech, has gradually moved from the realms of psychology and philosophy into linguistics, necessitating an interdisciplinary approach to its analysis. This growing interest among linguists highlights the need to study not only the speech itself but also the empathetic sema it conveys. Empathetic speech is primarily constructed to express concern, provide consolation, and offer comfort by acknowledging the emotions and inner state of the interlocutor.

According to the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language, the term *hamdardlik* (empathy/sympathy) is defined as “a feeling of shared sorrow, pain, or grief with someone else” and “to offer comforting words to alleviate someone's sadness or express solidarity with a grieving person.”

The inclination to help others, share kindness, and support those in hardship is deeply embedded in Uzbek culture and identity. Naturally, this tendency has shaped the emergence and frequent use of related linguistic expressions in everyday speech. In Islam as well, consoling those in distress and sharing their pain is considered a meritorious act.

Within empathetic speech, the use of introductory words, interjections, paremiological units, and phraseologisms serves to intensify the empathetic sema. Below are examples of emotionally charged utterances containing such expressions:

Pain, sorrow, and troubles are an inheritance from our ancestors. The poet wrote: “The world’s wealth is mine, but why this grief? / My body was irrigated with the waters of sorrow from the beginning.”

Enough, don’t cry, dear! Your heart must be bleeding from so much crying.

I would give my life for you, my dear child. Please don’t cry too much. Your father was a saintly man.

Don’t torment your soul so much, my daughter. Death comes to us all.

(Dard, g’am, tashvishlar Atomizdan bizga meros. Shoir bunday misralarni bejizga bitmagan:

Jahon mulki manim mulkim, bilmam bu g’am nimandandur?

Azalda g’am suvi bilan sug’orilgan badandandur.

Bo’ldi, yig’lamang, o’rgilay! Yig’layverib jigar bag’ringiz xun bo’ldi-ku!

Jonim fido senga, o’rgilay, jon bolam, ko’p yig’layvermagin. Otaginang jannati inson edilar.

Bir joningizni bunchalik o’rtayvermang, qizim, o’lim har kimning boshida bor.)

Here, expressions like “irrigated with the waters of sorrow,” “heart bleeding,” “tormented soul,” and “give my life” intensify the empathetic tone and increase the emotional-expressive depth of the speech.

Like phrasemes, paremiological units—such as proverbs and wise sayings—also enhance the persuasive power and aesthetic appeal of empathetic speech when used appropriately:

Death lies between the eyebrow and the eyelid, my child. These hardships come to everyone. Don’t let grief overcome you. Be patient.

Your father was a good man, my son, but what can we say? As the saying goes: “Death is certain, inheritance is lawful.”

Don’t be defeated by worldly sorrows: there is no river without flow, no world without death.

My child, don’t cry too much. Your mother’s time had come—she was almost 100. Life had become too difficult. After all, they say: “Pain is bad, but old age caused by pain is worse.”

(O’lim qosh bilan qovoqning orasida bo’ladi, bolam, bu ko’rguliklar har kimning boshida bor. G’amga yengilma, sabrli bo’l.

Otangiz yaxshi inson edilar, o’g’lim, ammo nima ham deymiz “o’lim – haq, meros – halol”, degan gap bor.

Dunyo g'amiga bunchalik yengilmaslik kerak: o'tgusiz daryo, o'limsiz dunyo bo'lmas. Bolam ko'p yig'lamang, onangizning to'yi bo'lyapti: 5 kam 100 ga kirgandilar. Bundan buyog'i yashash ham qiyin bo'lib qolgandi. Axir aytishadi-ku, "dard yomon, darddan qarilik yomon" deb.)

In addition to proverbs (maqol) and sayings (matal), wise expressions can also be used in empathetic speech, provided they carry an empathetic meaning. However, it is essential to fully understand their content before using them. Inappropriate use of any linguistic unit can diminish the quality of speech. For example, it would be inappropriate to use proverbs related to joy, fatigue, or aging at a funeral. Instead, proverbs with comforting and consoling meanings are more suitable.

Everyone leaves this world eventually, my dear—some sooner, some later. As our people say: “When death comes, even the judge dies.”

My friend, I know separation feels worse than death, but please pull yourself together. Dear child, stop worrying so much—I can't bear it either. But what can I do? If I speak, I'll burn my tongue; if I stay silent, I'll burn my heart.

(Bu dunyodan hamma o'tguvchi, o'rgilay, kimdir erta, kimdir kech. Axir xalqimizda matal bor: "Ajaj yetsa eshak o'ladi, qazo yetsa, qozi o'ladi".

Do'stim, bilaman, ayriliq – o'limdan qattiq, ammo o'zingni qo'lga ol.

Jon bolam, bo'ldi siqilavermagin, men ham chiday olmayapman. Lekin nima qilay? Aytsam tilim kuyadi, aytmasam – dilim.)

CONCLUSION:

Just as in other speech forms, the appropriate use of phraseologisms, paremiological units, and other linguistic elements in empathetic speech can significantly enhance its emotional power and aesthetic appeal. This allows the empathetic content to become more vivid and impactful. However, even the smallest inappropriately used expression can negatively affect the quality, expressiveness, and emotional tone of the speech.

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